

RESTORING TRADITIONAL ARABLE PRACTICES LIKE 'BOLLE AKKERS': THE ROLE OF AGROFORESTRY IN REVITALIZING HERITAGE FARMING SYSTEMS

1. Bolle fields in the Waasland region (Het Groene Waasland) 2. Barbierbeek Valley 3. Bolle fields in the Waasland region (Het Groene Waasland) 4. Barbierbeek Valley, maize and poplar

WHAT AND WHY

Rounded fields, or "bolle akkers" are a typical landscape feature of the Waasland, a historic region in northern Belgium. Archaeological research suggests that these characteristic, square rounded fields were likely created in the 14th and 15th centuries to improve drainage and soil fertility. This was necessary due to the clayey subsoil, which poorly drains water.

For centuries, these rounded fields, often bordered by pollarded willows or poplars, shaped the unique landscape of the area. Today, however, they are threatened by agricultural intensification. Agroforestry and the promotion of agroforestry practices can serve as a lever to preserve this special agricultural heritage. At the same time, they can contribute to greater biodiversity, reposition agriculture as a buffer zone between nature and urban areas, and play a role in combating climate change.

Keywords: landscape features, agricultural heritage, tree rows and hedgerows, ecological connections, and local collaboration are key elements in creating resilient and sustainable farming systems

HOW THE CHALLENGE IS ADDRESSED

The creation of the rounded fields was historically a response to the increasing demand for farmland and food. To form the rounded surface, the soil along the four sides of a plot was partially excavated on a slope, after which the land was plowed from the outside inward. On at least two sides, a wide and deep ditch was constructed. At a depth of approximately 60 to 80 cm below the original ground level, a strip-shaped widening of 3 to 4 meters was made. From this strip, a central dividing ditch was dug, measuring 1 to 1.5 meters in width and depth. This created two terraces on either side, each over 1 meter wide. On these terraces, hedgerows were planted with tree species such as beech, willow, oak, alder, plane, and poplar.

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ADVANTAGES

The restoration and replanting of tree rows and hedgerows in agricultural areas is more relevant today than ever before. Although preserving rounded fields is valuable from a heritage perspective, the ecological and climate benefits of tree rows and hedgerows outweigh this. These green structures provide tangible advantages for biodiversity, water management, carbon storage, and potential income streams for farmers.

Hedgerows strengthen the landscape structure and restore ecological connectivity. They increase biodiversity and create a resilient landscape in which agriculture again serves as a buffer between nature on one side and industry or residential areas on the other. Thanks to their ability to absorb water during heavy rainfall, they improve drainage of surrounding fields.

Additionally, tree rows act as natural windbreaks. They protect crops from wind damage and reduce evaporation during dry periods, enhancing crop resilience in times of climate change. Their root systems increase the organic carbon content of the soil, thereby promoting fertility.

By combining crop rotations (e.g., clover, wheat, hemp, or cover crops) with tree rows, an agroforestry system is created that not only generates higher yields but also contributes to carbon farming and biomass production. Trees like poplar can also serve as raw materials for bio-based products, which are essential for the transition to a circular economy supported by the EU Green Deal.

Finally, hedgerows encourage local cooperation, especially regarding the management of tree rows and woody structures and provide ecosystem services to the surrounding area. They contribute to enhanced soil care and support thoughtful landscape development. In this way, a versatile and future-proof agricultural model grows, where ecology, economy, and heritage mutually reinforce each other.

HIGHLIGHTS:

- **Bolle fields in the Waasland are of historical value and can be preserved through agroforestry value chains.**
- **Tree lines and hedgerows improve water management, enhance soil fertility, and act as natural windbreaks.**
- **Agroforestry with trees like poplar supports the circular economy, promotes carbon farming, and strengthens local collaboration and landscape structure.**

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**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101086563. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.